

Effects of Think Pair Share (TPS) and Peer-Tutoring (PT) Learning Strategies on Senior Secondary School Students' Achievement in Physics in Awka Education Zone

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ABSTRACT

The study determined the effects of Think Pair Share (TPS) and Peer-Tutoring (PT) teaching strategies on students' achievement in Physics in Awka Education zone. The study was guided by two (2) research questions and three (3) research hypotheses. The design of the study was Quasi-experimental design. The population was 2249 SSS II Physics students in Awka Education zone. The sample size 397 SSS II Physics students. Purposive sampling technique was used to sample the coeducational schools. The instrument used for the study was Physics Achievement Test (PAT) which was developed by the researcher. PAT was made up of two sections; Sections A and B. Section A requested for the respondents' bio-data while section B contained 50-multiple choice questions. PAT was validated by three experts from the Department of Science Education, University of Nigeria Nsukka. PAT was tested using 40 respondents in Onitsha Education zone and was found to be reliable with the KR-20 index of 0.79. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer research questions while ANCOVA was used to test the research hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. In testing the research hypothesis, the null hypothesis (H_0) was rejected when the significance of F (value of the test statistics) is less than 0.05. Otherwise do not reject at 0.05. The study discovered that Think Pair Share (TPS) is the most effective teaching method that can boost students' achievement in Physics more than Peer-Tutoring (PT). Thus, the study recommended Physics teachers should use TPS more often than PT in teaching Physics to the Senior Secondary School Physics students.

Keynotes: Physics, Peer-Tutoring (PT), Think Pair Share (TPS), Awka Education zone, Students' Achievement, Gender

Introduction

Science education is the process of teaching and learning science concepts, principles, and methodologies (Treagust, and Won, 2023). Science education involves fostering students' understanding of the natural world through inquiry, experimentation, observation, and critical thinking. Science education improves the quality of life. According to Loucks (2021), understanding science helps in making informed health, safety, and environmental decisions. In Nigeria secondary schools, science education is introduced at junior and senior levels. At secondary school level, the science education subjects that are offered are Chemistry, Physics, Biology, Agriculture, Mathematics, Computer Studies, Data Science and Forestry. Among all the science subjects taught at Senior Secondary school level, Physics remains the only subject that teaches about matter, its composition, properties, structure, behavior, and the changes it undergoes during chemical reactions. Physics is known as the Central Science, which bridges the physical and life sciences, bridging fields such as physics, biology, geology, and environmental science. Physics is a discipline of questioning, experimenting, inquiring and thinking, which engage students in innovation and creativity (Fasanya, Joel, Ahmed and Oche, 2023). Bawan and Udo (2019) established that learning Physics offers the student an opportunity to think critically, reason analytically and acquire the spirit of enquiry. This is why he asserted that: Physics is crucial for effective living in the modern age of science and technology. Given its application in industry and many other professions, every student must be given an opportunity to acquire some of its concepts, principles, and skills. Physics deals with the study of matter, energy, its conservation, forces, cause, effect, and their interactions in nature. According to Jegede and Adedayo

(2023), Nigerian national aim of teaching Physics in secondary schools is to produce young scientists who will be able to design the technological devices that will make day-to-day activities easier and living more comfortable. Daramola and Omosewo (2022) argued that the advancement of any nation depends on its worthwhile technological infrastructure and development.

The teaching and learning outcomes of this all-important subject, Physics need serious attention in order to enhance Nigeria's technological development. This is because according to Ladipo (2019), there is an increasing low enrolment in physics in schools and tertiary institutions in Nigeria and student performance has continued to witness a downward trend. Ezeife (2016) pointed to the fact that there are increasing conditions for underachievement and slow learning. Isola (2020) reported that Physics is one of the science subjects remains one of the most difficult subjects in the school curriculum. Thus, efforts should be made to revisit the teaching and learning of Physics with the aim of catering for the needs of the society for which it is designed in line with the realities of the 21st century. One of the scholars who have tried looking at the teaching and learning in general is Lev Vygotsky. According to Lev Vygotsky (1978), learning of Physics occurs when students collaborate with others within their Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD). This implies that when Physics teachers are teaching Physics, they should use Collaborative Learning Method.

Collaborative learning is a method where students work in groups to complete experiments, solve problems, or discuss concepts. Collaborative learning builds communication and teamwork skills, encourages peer-to-peer learning and develops problem-solving skills (Putri, Sedyati, Zulianto, 2023). Collaborative teaching methods that are student-centered approach include Peer-Tutoring, Project Based Learning (PBL), Inquiry Based Learning (IBL), Team Achievement Divisions (TAD), Think Pair Share (TPS) and Peer-tutoring, Teaching Strategy (JTS). Among these Collaborative Learning Method, Think Pair Share (TPS) and Peer-Tutoring methods would be looked at. This is because many scholars have researched on them and found them effective. In a separate studies done on think-pair-share technique, Achufusi, Okonkwo, and Wisdom (2024) found out that students taught using the think-pair-share strategy performed better and had a higher retention in chemistry than those taught using the lecture method. The finding of Achufusi, Okonkwo, and Wisdom gives a positive indication that if students are taught Physics using Think-Pair-Share (TPS), the students' achievement in Physics will enhance while for Peer-Tutoring (PT) teaching strategy, Costouros (2020) showed that students taught using Peer-Tutoring learning strategy performed significantly better than those taught using lecture method. The findings of Costouros (2020) give a positive suggestion that if students are taught Physics using Peer-Tutoring teaching strategy, their achievement in Physics would be enhanced. Since these scholars failed to compare the efficacy of these two in teaching students Physics, the researcher adopted to embark on this study with the aim to determine among the two methods, which of them is effective in boosting students' achievement in Physics.

Think-Pair-Share (TPS) is a collaborative learning strategy that involves three stages: Think, Pair and Share. When students think, they think individually about a question or problem. Then the students are paired so they discuss their thoughts with partners. The pairs then share their ideas with the larger group or class. Think-Pair-Share (TPS) encourages students to process information individually before discussing, which enhances retention and comprehension, (Jimoh, 2024). Students clarify their understanding by articulating their thoughts during the "pair" and "share" stages. Students who are exposed to Think-Pair-Share (TPS) receive immediate feedback from peers, which helps them identify and correct misunderstandings. TPS makes students feel more comfortable sharing in pairs, thus boosting their confidence and engagement (Manda, 2024).

While for Peer-Tutoring (PT) teaching strategy is typically conceptualized as stemming from constructivist theories of learning, such as the constructivism of Jean Piaget, and the social constructivism of Lev Vygotsky. According to Piaget's approach, adult-student interaction is less effective in promoting learning because the adult's natural authority leads to asymmetry that renders the student a more passive recipient of knowledge and instruction (Piaget, 1959). The Peer Tutoring (PT) teaching strategy refers to a variety of teaching strategies that involves students working together face to face in pairs or small groups to accomplish a mutual educational goal or task (O' Donnell, 2016). Peer-Tutoring is aimed at meeting the special needs of learners who in one way or the other have difficulty in coping effectively during teaching and learning in the classroom. Peer-Tutoring is perceived by educators as a valuable educational activity that enhances learning through active participation. The concepts of these Peer-Tutoring and Think-Pair-share learning strategies implies that these learning strategies will be effective when used in teaching

Physics but the learning method that will be more effective in students' achievement in Physics is not known by the researcher. Thus, the researcher shall determine the effects of Think Pair Share (TPS) and Peer-Tutoring (PT) learning strategies on senior secondary school students' achievement in Physics. Students' achievement in Physics is a key indicator of students' mastery of Physics curriculum content taught. It is the exhibition of knowledge attained by students in a Physics designed test assigned by the teachers. Thus, the researcher would design a Physics Test that he would use to determine the extent at which the Physics students may have assimilated what they are taught using Think Pair Share (TPS) and Peer-Tutoring (PT) learning strategies. The study would also determine the efficacy of students' gender on students' achievement in Physics when taught using Think Pair Share (TPS) and Peer-Tutoring (PT) learning strategies. This is because Gender is a moderating variable in this research and the controversies among scholars on whether gender has influence on students' achievement in Physics or not. Physics is often perceived as male-dominated subject as Obasi (2017) reported that the male students achieve better than the female students. However, Lindner and Makarova, (2024) disclosed that when girls are given equal opportunities, supportive environments, and exposure to relatable role models in Physics, their achievement in Physics can match or surpass those of boys. In contrary to these assertions, Toni, Gonzalez, Odic, Block and Baron (2021) insisted that there is no difference in the students' performance in Physics. According to Toni, et al (2021), the performance of students rely on the individual students and environment and not on gender. Thus, the researcher wants to determine if the methods are gender friendly or gender bias.

Purpose of the Study

The aim of this study was to determine the effects of Think Pair Share (TPS) and Peer-Tutoring (PT) teaching strategies on students' achievement in Physics in Awka Education zone. Specifically, the study determined;

1. The mean achievement scores of students taught Physics using TPS, those taught using PT and those taught using Lecture method in Awka educational zone.
2. The mean achievement scores of male and female students taught Physics using TPS, those taught using Peer-Tutoring Learning method in Awka educational zone.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study

1. What is the mean achievement scores of students taught Physics using TPS, those taught using PT and those taught using Lecture method in Awka educational zone?
2. What is the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught Physics using TPS and those taught using PT?

Research Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses which were tested at 0.05 levels of significance guided the study.

- H0 1: There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught Physics using TPS, those taught using PT and those taught using Lecture method in Awka educational zone
- H0 2: There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught Physics using TPS and those taught using PT in Awka educational zone
- H0 3: There is no significant interaction between gender and learning strategies on students' achievement in Physics in Awka educational zone

Research Methods

The design of the study was Quasi-experimental design. The population was 2249 SSS II Physics students in Awka Education zone as at 2024/2025 academic session (Post Primary Schools Service Commission, PPSSC, Awka zone). The sample size was 397 SSS II Physics students. The sample size was the total number of three sampled intact classes in each three schools selected from Awka Education zone. Purposive sampling technique was used to sample the coeducational schools. The instrument used for the study was Physics Achievement Test (PAT) which was developed by the researcher. The instrument was

made up of two sections; Sections A and B. Section A requested for the respondents' bio-data while section B contained 50-multiple choice questions. PAT was validated by two experts in Physics education and one expert in Measurement and Evaluation from the Department of Science Education, University of Nigeria Nsukka and their comments were incorporated in the final draft of the PAT. PAT was tested using 40 respondents in Onitsha Education zone. The reliability KR-20 index of 0.79 was obtained, which means that PAT was reliable. The experimental procedure include; obtaining permission from the sampled schools, training of the sampled Physics teachers for three (3) weeks which were the study's research assistant, the research assistants administering the pre-PAT on the first week, the research assistants administering he treatment using the lesson notes prepared by the researcher for four weeks and at the end of the day, the research assistants administering the post-PAT. The scores obtained from the pre-and post-PAT were analyzed using the SPSS. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer research questions while ANCOVA was used to test the research hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. In testing the research hypothesis, the null hypothesis (H_0) was rejected when the significance of F (value of the test statistics) is less than 0.05. Otherwise do not reject at 0.05.

Results

Research Question 1

What are the mean achievement scores and standard deviations of students taught Physics using Think Pair Share (TPS) (Experimental group 1), Peer-Tutoring (PT) (Experimental group 2) and Expository method (Control group) in both pretest and posttest?

Table 1: Mean Achievement Scores and Standard Deviations of students taught Physics in both pretest and posttest

Groups	Number	Pretest		Post-test		Gained Mean
		Mean (\bar{x})	Standard Deviation (s)	Mean (\bar{x})	Standard Deviation (s)	
Experimental 1	132	46.67	7.25	63.70	7.46	17.04
Experimental 2	133	45.20	7.64	58.60	7.74	13.40
Control	132	45.00	6.49	51.55	6.71	6.55
Total	397					

Table 1 displays the result of Mean Achievement Scores and Standard Deviations of students taught Physics in both pretest and posttest. From the results in Table 1, it shows that learning takes place. This is because the three (3) groups achieve higher posttest mean scores than their pretest mean scores in Physics. However, the posttest mean achievement scores of the experimental groups are higher than the posttest mean achievement scores of the control group. The table 1 further shows that the students taught Physics using TPS (Experimental Group 1) gained highest with the gained mean of 17.04 (the pretest mean score of 46.67 (sd= 7.25) and posttest mean score of 63.70 (sd = 7.46) follows by the students taught using PT (Experimental group 2) with the pretest mean score of 45.20 (sd =7.64) and posttest mean score of 58.60 (sd = 7.74) while the least is the students taught with Expository method (Control Group) whose pretest mean score is 45.00 (sd = 6.49) and posttest mean score is 51.55 (sd = 6.71). Also, the results shows that the posttest mean scores of the students in experimental and control groups are homogeneous since that the differences in their standard deviations are closed.

Research Question 2

What are the mean achievement scores and standard deviations of male and female students in the experimental groups?

Table 2: Mean Achievement Scores and Standard Deviations of Male and Female Students in Experimental Groups

Gender	Number	Males			Female		
		Number	Mean (\bar{x})	Standard Deviation (s)	Number	Mean (\bar{x})	Standard Deviation (s)

Experimental 1	132	83	62.10	6.94	49	66.43	7.58
Experimental 2	133	81	59.70	7.43	52	56.88	7.96
Total	265	164	60.9	7.19	101	61.66	7.77

Table 2 showed the mean achievement scores and standard deviations of male and female students in experimental groups. The results of the data analyses in table 2 showed that the female students slightly has higher mean score and higher standard deviation of 61.66 and 7.77 respectively than their male counterparts in Experimental group that has the mean score of 60.90 and 7.19 respectively with the mean difference of 0.76 and standard deviation difference of 0.58. The slightly differences in both mean scores and standard deviation shows that their mean scores of the male and female students in the Experimental Groups are uniform since that their standard deviations are closed.

Table 3: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of the Mean Achievement Scores of the Experimental and Control Groups

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
Corrected Model	27000.995 ^a	6	4500.166	1952.658	.000	
Intercept	1535.629	1	1535.629	666.322	.000	
PreTAT	19263.743	1	19263.743	8358.691	.000	
GROUP	4514.185	2	2257.092	979.370	.000	S
GENDER	1.067	1	1.067	.463	.497	NS
GROUP * GENDER	6.552	2	3.276	1.422	.243	NS
Error	898.808	390	2.305			
Total	1391979.000	397				
Corrected Total	27899.804	396				

a. R Squared = .968 (Adjusted R Squared = .967)

b. WHERE S = Significant at $P < .05$; NS = Not Significant at $P > .05$

Table 3 shows the Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of the Mean Achievement Scores of the Experimental and Control Groups. The Table 3 is used to answer null hypotheses 1 to 3.

Hypothesis 1

HO₁: There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught Physics using TPS, PT and Expository method (Control group) in both pretest and posttest.

From the result of ANCOVA in Table 3, it is observed that Group (treatment and Control) has an F-value of 979.370 and is significant at 0.000. Since 0.000 is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis 1 is rejected as stated. Hence, the study concluded that there is significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught Physics using Think Pair Share (TPS) (Experimental group 1), Peer-Tutoring (PT)(Experimental group 2) and Expository method (Control group). Thus, table 4 would be used to check the group that is superior using the Bonferroni Technique.

Table 4: Multiple Comparisons Post-Hoc Test Using Bonferroni Technique with Dependent Variable of Students' Achievement in Physics

(I) Group	(J) Group	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	
EXP GROUP 1 (TPS)	EXP GROUP 2(PT)	3.724*	.194	.000	SUP
	CONTROL GROUP 1 (EXPOSITORY)	8.577*	.195	.000	SUP
EXP GROUP 2(PT)	EXP GROUP 1 (TPS)	-3.724*	.194	.000	NSUP
	CONTROL GROUP 1 (EXPOSITORY)	4.853*	.192	.000	SUP
CONTROL GROUP 1 (EXPOSITORY)	EXP GROUP 1 (TPS)	-8.577*	.195	.000	NSUP
	EXP GROUP 2(PT)	-4.853*	.192	.000	NSUP

Based on estimated marginal means

*. The mean difference is significant at the .05 level.

b. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Bonferroni.

WHERE SUP = Superior at $P < .05$; NSUP = Not Superior at $P > .05$

Table 4 shows the Multiple Comparisons Post-Hoc Test Using Bonferroni Technique with Dependent Variable of Students' Achievement in Physics. The table shows that the pair wise comparisons of Students' Achievement scores in Physics of Experimental group 1 (TPS) and Experimental group 2 (PT) is 3.724 which is significant at .000 and since 0.000 is less than 0.05, it implies that the Experimental Group 1 (TPS) is significantly superior to Experimental Group 2 (PT) in students' achievement in Physics. The table shows that the pairwise comparisons of Students' Achievement scores in Physics of Experimental group 1 (TPS) and Control group (Expository method) is 8.577 which is significant at .000 and since 0.000 is less than 0.05, it implies that the Experimental group 1 (TPS) is significantly superior to Control Group (Expository method) in students' achievement in Physics. The implication of these findings is that the students taught Physics using Think Pair Share (TPS) is significantly superior and significantly achieved better than their counterparts taught Physics using Peer-Tutoring (PT) and Expository method. Also, the table shows that the pair wise comparisons of Students' Achievement scores in Physics of Experimental group 2 (PT) and Control Group (Expository Method) is 4.853 which is significant at .000 and since 0.000 was less than 0.05, it implies that the Experimental group 2 (PT) is significantly superior to Control Group (Expository Method) in students' achievement in Physics. The implication of these findings is that the students taught Physics using Peer-Tutoring (PT) superiorly and significantly achieved better than their counterparts taught Physics using Expository method.

Hypothesis 2

HO₂: There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students in the experimental groups.

From the result of ANCOVA in Table 3, Gender (Male and Female) has an F-value of .463 and is not significant at 0.497. Since 0.497 is not less than 0.05, the null hypothesis 2 is accepted as stated. Hence, the study concluded that there is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students in the experimental groups in Physics.

Hypothesis 3

HO₃: There is no interaction effect of gender and teaching methods on students' achievement in Physics.

From the result of ANCOVA in Table 3, Group*Gender (Interaction) has an F-value of 1.422 and is significant at 0.243. Since 0.243 is not less than 0.05, the null hypothesis 3 is accepted as stated. Hence, the study concluded that there is no significant interaction effect of gender and teaching methods on students' achievement in Physics.

Major Findings

From the results in Tables 1 to 8, the study discovers the followings;

1. The students taught Physics using Think Pair Share (TPS) is significantly superior and significantly achieved better than their counterparts taught Physics using Peer-Tutoring (PT) and Expository method and that the students taught Physics using Peer-Tutoring (PT) superiorly and significantly achieved better than their counterparts taught Physics using Expository method.
2. There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students in the experimental groups in Physics.
3. There is no significant interaction effect of gender and teaching methods on students' achievement in Physics

Discussion of the Findings

The study discovered that the students that were taught Physics using the Think Pair Share (TPS) significantly achieved highest while the students taught Physics using PT achieved higher than those taught using Expository method. This finding contradicts the finding of George (2025) revealed that there was no

significant effect between students' taught with PT and those taught with conventional method. This finding implies that when students are taught Physics using TPS, their achievement in Physics would be greatly boosted more than their counterparts taught using PT. This is because according to Jimoh (2024), TPS encourages students to process information individually before discussing, which enhances comprehension in Physics. TPS improves conceptual understanding, ensuring that all students actively engaged, making it easier for them to grasp complex ideas like states of matter, energy transfer or chemical bonding. TPS strategy plays a great role on students' retention and makes students to be actively involved in thinking, discussing, and sharing, making the learning process more interactive and enjoyable.

Also, the study revealed that there were no significant differences between the male and female students' achievement and retention in Physics. This finding tally with the finding of Toni, Gonzalez, Odic, Block, and Baron (2021) who insisted that there is no difference in the students' performance in Physics. According to Toni, et al (2021), the performance of students rely on the individual students and environment and not on gender. Finally, there are no significant interaction between the teaching methods and gender. These findings tally with the finding of Neboh (2009) who found no interaction effect between gender and instructional model. These findings imply that the achievement of male and female students did not vary due to variation in the instructional methods used which includes TPS, PT and Expository Method. This is because the instructional strategies gives all the students equal opportunities to grow in the comprehension of Physics.

Conclusion

The study examined the effects of Think Pair Share (TPS) and Peer-Tutoring (PT) teaching strategies on students' achievement in Physics in Awka Education zone. The study discovered that Think Pair Share (TPS) is the most effective teaching method that can boost students' achievement in Physics. Thus, the study recommended Physics teachers should use TPS more often than PT in teaching Physics to the Senior Secondary School Physics students.

Recommendations

Based on the implications and findings of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Physics teachers should ensure that the Senior Secondary School Physics students are taught Physics using TPS more often than PT.
2. Federal/State Governments and Post Primary Schools Service Commission, PPSSC, Awka zone should therefore make sure that Physics teachers make use of TPS more often to teach students Physics. In case where it is not possible to use, the Physics teachers can then use PT to teach students Physics.
3. Federal/State governments and other relevant professional bodies should sponsor seminars, conferences, workshops, refresher courses on the use of Think Pair Share (TPS) more than Peer-Tutoring (PT) in teaching Physics since that TPS has proven to be most effective in teaching Physics.
4. Physics educators involved in the curriculum development should restructure the Senior Secondary School Physics Syllabus and textual materials that can create opportunities for students to use Think Pair Share (TPS) for the teaching and learning of Physics.
5. Gender Discrimination should not be allowed in the act of teaching students Physics.

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